

TAKING BACK POWER: SELF-DEFENSE AND FEMALE TRIUMPH IN ARTEMISIA GENTILESCHI

Francisca Sousa

Porto University of Fine Arts (FBAUP: Faculdade de Belas Artes da Universidade do Porto)
i2ADS - Instituto de Investigação em Arte, Design e Sociedade, Portugal.

ABSTRACT:

Throughout history, the concept of power has been a central theme in the art world. Represented in its various contexts - political, social, physical, sexual - power can be seen as a complex idea between physical domination and an abstract force. Often associated in art with violence and male brutality, power is especially enacted over the female body, inevitably through some sort of game of domination and submission. But how does a female artist portray power?

This essay explores the work of the baroque artist Artemisia Gentileschi as a space of resistance and subversion, challenging the predominant patriarchal gaze of her time. Through striking pictorial compositions, intense physicality, powerful female characters and sharp objects, Artemisia redefines violence and takes her power back.

Her heroines - far from being passive subjects - are portrayed as active agents of their own destinies, often reclaiming control and dominance. The use of domestic tools as weapons, the psychological depth of her figures, and the visceral intensity of her compositions contribute to a powerful visual language that subverts traditional gender roles. Artemisia's legacy extends far beyond her time, resonating in contemporary discussions about representation, gender, and feminism. Her work is testament of the enduring struggle for female empowerment in art and society. She's a woman that transforms herself into a blade in order to face trauma.

Keywords: feminism, power, self defense, space, Bourgeois, Gentileschi.

* Intro

“In Utopia—that is to say, in a world in which the power structure was such that both men and women equally could be represented clothed or unclothed in a variety of poses and positions without any implications of domination or submission.” (Nochlin, 1989: 30)

The nature of interventions by feminist art criticism and art history, along with gender studies, has made visible the need to rethink dominant modes of representation—both past and present. Throughout history, particularly in the Western context, it is evident that women have occupied a place of passivity and vulnerability, predominantly contemplated in art as muses and sources of inspiration for the gaze of male creators. Consequently, a significant portion of the images depicting women portrays narratives of their silence, their physical exploitation, and their association with domestic tasks - they occupy the background of a world led by men. This premise only seems to break away from the dominant discourse with the emergence and recognition of female artists, who gradually took the liberty to create exceptions and establish a more inclusive visual language.

Feminism and women's liberation movements have led to a profound transformation of contemporary society's content, in an urgent effort to shed light on gender inequalities and the issues stemming from the exclusion of minorities. Their activist voices reflect a prolonged authoritarian and patriarchal dominance, primarily imposed on the female (and also the enslaved) body, with evidence of this oppression extending into the present. Thus, the body is now a central focus in contemporary female artists' thinking - a space for the construction and deconstruction of identity, for oppression and resistance. The marks of power are inscribed on the body¹.

The triadic concept of “woman-art-power”² presented in Linda Nochlin's essay is an attempt to unravel the various power discourses related to gender differences in visual narratives. The idea of domination/submission is part of a binary dynamic between a character who holds "greater strength" or superior

¹ MACEDO, Ana Gabriela, (2011), *Mulheres, arte e poder: uma narrativa de contrapoder?*, Brasil: Estudos de Literatura Brasileira Contemporânea, p.3.

² NOCHLIN, Linda (1989), *Women, Art and Power and other Essays*, London:Thames and Hudson, p.2.

authority and one of lesser "vis." From the depiction of explicit physical brutality to psychological or symbolic violence, there are multiple ways in which this concept - power - operates, which I seek to explore here from the perspective of the female artist and the counter-power narratives she creates.

Although it was particularly from the 1970s onward that the mission to reclaim power and control over one's own body was undertaken by female artists - who multiplied as they found their legitimate spot in the art world - there are a few case studies that precede these movements. One particular example is the Italian Baroque painter Artemisia Gentileschi, whose work I intend to discuss here. In her paintings, the iconography of empowerment is sustained by concepts of justice and self-defense, representing infamous heroines who disarmed and emasculated unsuspecting men.

*

“A great woman in an age we usually associate with great men.”

(JONES, 2020: 5)

When, in 2020, the National Gallery in London announced a major solo exhibition of Artemisia Gentileschi, the world was invited to look back at the past and recognize how a Baroque artist, nearly 400 years ago, managed to articulate a voice that still echoes in contemporary times. Self-representation, feminist expression³, and a singular ability to manifest her own point of view make her work an almost inconceivable achievement for her time - an era dominated by male influence. In the space that only she knew how to occupy as both a painter and a woman, her greatest weapon was self-defense.

Coming from a family background that granted her free access to the atelier from childhood, Artemisia Gentileschi, an apprentice to her father, stands out in the Baroque period not only for her technical virtuosity and rigorous realism but, above all, for expanding the role of the female protagonist in her narratives. A faithful follower of Caravaggio, Gentileschi used chiaroscuro to depict religious themes imbued with striking expressions and sinuous gestures that cut through the air with ferocity. Blades of swords, nails pressed against the neck, bodies restrained by assertive hands, and faces revealing an instinct for survival—these are the symbols of power present in her work, reflecting a social reality that was both dangerous and intimidating for the women of her time.

When considering Artemisia's history of rape - shared by countless other women - a connection emerges between reality and fiction, between heroine and artist, between tragedy and vengeance, culminating on the canvas but also adding something more. The sexual abuse she suffered at the age of 17 at the hands of the painter and family friend Agostino Tassi, followed by harsh trials to prove her innocence in court, left a profound mark on her but did not define her.

Observing one of her early works, “Susanna and the Elders” (1610) - a story taken from the Old Testament in which a young woman, bathing in the

³ “The artist's large and growing audience, strongly female, savours her bold feminist expression and calls it just that. Scholars sniff that Artemisia’s fans project a modern concept, anachronistically, on to an artist who painted before the term ‘feminist’ was invented.” (GARRARD, Mary D., 2020, *Artemisia Gentileschi and Feminism in Early Modern Europe*, Reaktion Books, p.7)

privacy of her garden, is suddenly confronted by two older men who cast lascivious glances at her - one understands the impact of Artemisia's voice and how it differs from male painters' reproductions of the same subject. In the 2021 conference "Power and Sexuality in Renaissance Art", Lisa Kaborycha presented a relevant perspective on this issue, analyzing how Susanna's body was represented by different artists and how these visual depictions helped shape misogynistic beliefs across Europe, reinforcing the polarized identity of women as either saints or sinners. In her analysis of works by Tintoretto (1555-56) and Alessandro Allori (1561), one observes the eroticization of the young woman's exposed body, as if it were a striptease⁴, and the use of iconography associated with courtesans of the period—excessively ornamented blonde hair and yellow veils, a color linked to prostitution. In Allori's painting, the luminous quality of the artwork accentuates Susanna's breasts and thighs, while one of the Elders slides his hand between her legs, transforming the painting into an inevitable appreciation of Susanna's carnal and sinful beauty, complicit in the crime. In the face of this moral ambiguity⁵, the viewer is distanced from the dramatic reality of the situation: harassment and attempted rape.

In Artemisia's painting, however, Susanna is depicted in a profoundly different manner—there is no playful eroticization of the scene, but rather a realistic sensation of threat and anguish. The artist had a unique ability to portray this conflict with seriousness and intensity. On the canvas, we see a trapped woman who wants to escape: Susanna's arms desperately push away her aggressors, her body recoils in distress, and her facial expression is neither ambiguous nor difficult to decipher. Laying bare this position of fragility in which the character finds herself—inevitable due to physical strength and numerical disadvantage—as a way to denounce an atrocity is, in itself, a symbolic form of empowerment. Although Susanna's body is ultimately submissive, it is

⁴ "She's almost in a scene of striptease with her clothes falling off of her, suggestively at her feet" (KABORYCHA, Lisa, 2021, *Power and Sexuality in Renaissance Art*. available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1BOTfXxaaxE&t=1068s>).

⁵ "Many would have undoubtedly believed that any woman who was naked in her garden was inherently inviting sexual advances. The expression on the elder's face has "you've got this coming to you" written all over it." (HASSLET, Tim, 2014, *The moral ambiguity of Alessandro Allori's Susanna and the Elders*. available at: <https://timothyhaslett.wordpress.com/2014/08/01/the-moral-ambiguity-of-alessandro-alloris-susanna-and-the-elders>)

crystallized in this work as a force of resistance and refusal against the attempt at male domination.

“This is one way that Artemisia Gentileschi changes art: simply by being female. When she paints a naked woman, it’s different from a man doing so. She sees the entire scene from a different point of view. Tintoretto sympathizes with Susanna but he also enjoys her. Artemisia, by contrast paints this as a scene of sheer torture.” (JONES, 2020: 21)

Image 1: *Susanna and the Elders*, Artemisia Gentileschi, oil on canvas, 1610.

One of Artemisia Gentileschi’s most remarkable works follows, where antagonism ceases to be subjective and instead appropriates the signs of power that permeate violence: *Judith Beheading Holofernes*, the 1620-21

version, currently exhibited at the Uffizi Gallery in Florence. In this story of female triumph and retaliation, the widow Judith, in order to save her city from occupation, seduces and intoxicates the opposing general, Holofernes, taking advantage of his drowsy state to assassinate him. Aided by her maid, Abra, she grabs a blade to cut off his head and free her people.

This heroic duo is immortalized by Artemisia in the depiction of the exact moment of the decapitation. Holofernes' head is still midway through the cut, his eyes are wide open; blood spurts through the air, onto the sheets and stains Judith's chest; the women's arms are strong and vigorous (reminiscent of Potiphar's wife in the relief by the artist Properzia de Rossi), ensuring that their prey does not escape. Here, both female characters share the protagonism, they both look youthful, strong, and determined - unlike versions of the same story by other artists, where Abra is often portrayed as a passive, elderly figure who merely observes without directly intervening in the action, as we can see in Caravaggio's 1599 interpretation.

In *Artemisia*, composition contains the dynamism and drama typical of the Baroque period⁶, as Weronika Malek notes, designed to impress the viewer through shock - similar to what can be seen today in the gore-style cinematography of Quentin Tarantino, for instance. "Judith Beheading Holofernes" is an explicit and highly effective iconographic representation of power, centered around the cutting edge of the sword, fully embracing its violent nature and proclaiming the artist's triumph over her transgressor. In this work, *Artemisia* metaphorically strikes her target:

"Artemisia also told the judges that she fought back and would have killed Tassi if she could. But instead of glancing off his chest like the knife she threw at him, Judith's sword has found its mark. She keeps cutting." (JONES, 2020: 38)

"The subject of the 'Judith Beheading Holofernes' relates to the traumatic event that Gentileschi experienced, and some sources have stated that Judith as the main protagonist in the painting is, in fact, a self-portrait of the artist herself." (GARRARD, 1989: 664)

⁶ "The dynamic and dramatic scene is typical for the Baroque Period, that Gentileschi's masterpiece comes from. Baroque style puts a strong emphasis on shocking and engaging the audience's feelings through emotionally stimulating scenes. Baroque artists were also inspired by theater: they used narrative, dynamism, and illusion in their work". (MALEK, Weronika (2013), *The Power of Judith and Artemisia*. available at: <https://fnewsmagazine.com/2013/11/the-power-of-judith-and-artemisia/>)

Image 2: *Judith Beheading Holofernes*, Artemisia Gentileschi, oil on canvas 1621.

In the painting “Jael and Sisera” (1620), Artemisia continues to explore the representation of female power, as if depicting a “battle of sexes.” She portrays the moment when the heroine Jael raises a hammer toward the head of the sleeping oppressor, General Sisera, ready to kill him.

The image is rendered with striking realism and tenebrist lighting, emphasizing the murder weapon - a tent peg/nail - a crucial detail in the iconography of this scene. The use of a domestic tool, seemingly harmless, reinforces the subversion of the traditional female role. This reversal of roles, in which the female heroine takes a stand appropriating male power⁷, echoes the

⁷ “In this gender role inversion, Artemisia subtly invokes the theme of woman-on-top (...). What animated the woman-on-top imagery was the laughable absurdity of a woman making a fool of a man by appropriating his power.” (GARRARD, Mary D., 2020, *Artemisia Gentileschi and Feminism in Early Modern Europe*, Reaktion Books, p.162)

voice of an artist who fought against gender violence and the dominant seventeenth-century conventions that sought to silence her and her peers.

The detail of Artemisia's signature is also intriguing, as it appears carved into a pilaster at the center of the painting, integrating herself into the narrative as if it had been inscribed just moments before Jael kills the general. Jael's arm positioning evokes the choreography of a stone worker. Reality and art blend together, and this possible self-representation is further enriched by another familiar face: the figure of General Sisera bears a strong resemblance to the artist Caravaggio, whom Artemisia admired. This could serve as an allegory for the creation of a masterpiece or even as a challenge to her male contemporaries. However, what truly triumphs here is her creative genius and her ability to craft her own universe - one that only Artemisia is in charge of:

“Lastly, in working on his head, Jael conveys that "Sisera" is her masterpiece because the Italian for it, *capolavoro*, literally means head-work. On the other hand, despite the demands of the story, it is likely that Artemisia's focus on Sisera's head conveys a more important meaning: that we should not get lost in the illusions of the exterior world but find peace (as Sisera/Caravaggio ironically does) in the inner reality of our minds.” (ABRAHAMS, 2014)

Image 3: Jael and Sisera, Artemisia Gentileschi, oil on canvas, 1620.

*** End**

Artemisia Gentileschi's work is inscribed within a space of resistance and subversion, where the semiotics of power challenges the predominant patriarchal gaze of her time. Through striking pictorial compositions, intense physicality of her infamous protagonists and sharp objects, Artemisia creates images in which violence becomes her own way of taking back power, fight for justice and defend herself - at times with a mix of pleasure - turning her into one of the most progressive and revolutionary artists of the Italian Baroque period.

More broadly, Artemisia's art is imbued with powerful symbols of female empowerment. Her heroines are not passive victims but active agents of their own destinies, often depicted in moments of defiance, triumph and resistance. Whether through the resolute strength of Judith, the unwavering determination of Jael, or the vulnerable yet resilient Susanna, Artemisia consistently reclaims narratives in which women assert control over their bodies and fates. In doing so, she not only carved a space for herself in a male-dominated artistic world but also created a visual language that continues to inspire feminist readings and contemporary art, since she placed female experience directly at the center of her work.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

ABRAHAMS, Simon (2014), *Artemisia Gentileschi's Jael and Sisera (1620)*, Available at:

https://www.everypainterpaintshimself.com/article/artemisia_gentileschis_jael_and_sisera_1620.

Butler, Judith (1990), *Problemas de Género*, Lisboa: Orfeu Negro, 2017.
EDITORS, P. (2015), *Body of Art*, Phaidon Press.

Garrard, Mary D. (1989), *Artemisia Gentileschi: The Image of the Female Hero in Italian Baroque Art*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.

Hooks, Bell (1984), *Teoria Feminista: Da Margem ao Centro*, Lisboa: Orfeu Negro, 2020.

Jones, Jonathan (2020), *Artemisia Gentileschi*, London: Laurence King.

Joseph-Lowery, Frédérique (2010), *Through the Eye of a Needle*. Available at:
<http://www.artnet.com/magazineus/features/lowery/louise-bourgeois6-15-10.asp>

Kaborycha, Lisa (2021), *Power and Sexuality in Renaissance Art*. Available at:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1BOTfXxaaxE&list=LL&index=3&t=853s>.

Kuspit, Donald (2008), *The Phallic Woman*. Available at:
<http://www.artnet.com/magazineus/features/kuspit/bourgeois-the-phallic-woman-11-3-10.asp>.

Macedo, Ana Gabriela (2011), *Mulheres, arte e poder: uma narrativa de contrapoder?*, Brasil: Estudos de Literatura Brasileira Contemporânea.

Miller, Juliet (2008), *Power and vulnerability in the work of Louise Bourgeois in The Creative Feminine and her Discontents*, London: Routledge.

Nochlin, Linda (1989). *Women, Art and Power and other Essays*, London: Thames and Hudson.

Piland, Sherry (1994). *Women Artists: A Historical, Contemporary and Feminist Bibliography*, PhilPapers.

Reilly, Maura (2015), *Women Artists. The Linda Nochlin Reader*, London: Thames and Hudson.

Vreeland, Susan (2002), *The Passion of Artemisia: A Novel*, London: Publish Penguin Books.